

the aryl residue to the α -amino unit with increasing pH. The overall processes involved in these changes are presented in Scheme 1.

That the acidity factor alone is not responsible for the switch over of the preference from the aryl to the amino group, became evident from studies with phenylalanine (1).

The reaction of (1) with Ru^{VIII} as stated previously, at pH 6, gave only phenylacetic acid (3) in 43% yields. Of particular relevance is the finding that even at pH 3, conditions under which tyrosine (2) exclusively yielded aspartic acid (4), phenylalanine (1) afforded a 76% yield of phenylacetic acid (3). Careful analysis of the reaction mixture revealed the complete absence of aspartic acid (4) (Scheme 2).

This result, when viewed in the context of the reported transformation of benzylamine to glycine in 60% yields in

the biphasic carbon tetrachloride-pH 3 phosphate buffer, with the preformed Ru^{VIII} largely sequestered in the organic phase⁷, would imply that the ring oxidation takes place in the organic phase and that of the amino group in the aqueous media.

The divergent behaviour of tyrosine (2) and phenylalanine (1) towards Ru^{VIII} at pH 3 under our conditions – resulting exclusively in, respectively, ring and amino group oxidation – can be rationalized on the basis of comparative susceptibilities of the ring and the fully protonated amino group. The acetonitrile enables the maintenance of a dynamic flux of the Ru^{VIII} species in the organic and aqueous phases. It is very reasonable to assume that, at this pH, the ring oxidation takes place at the interface and that of the amino group exclusively in the aqueous layer, a notion that is supported by the transformation of benzylamine to glycine and where the oxidizing species is almost exclusively in the organic layer (*vide supra*). Assuming that the susceptibility of the amino group in phenylalanine (1) and tyrosine (2) towards oxidation be of the same order, the course of the reaction of these substrates would be governed by the propensity for ring oxidation.

Reasonable pathways for the changes involved are illustrated in Scheme 3. As shown here, the course of the oxidation is controlled by the susceptibility for ring oxidation on one hand (path a) and the facility of the formation of the key ruthenium bound intermediate (6) on the other (path b'). At pH 3, the latter pathway would be greatly discouraged. Thus, the formation of aspartic acid (4) from tyrosine (2) should be ascribed to the dominance of path a, whilst the exclusive isolation of phenylacetic acid (3) from phenylalanine (1)

reflects the operation of path b', against heavy odds, arising from vastly decreased propensity for the benzene ring oxidation.

A noteworthy feature is that at pH 3, the yield of phenylacetic acid (**3**; 76%) is substantially higher than at pH 6 (43%), in apparent contradiction to expectations. At the higher pH, benzoic acid is isolated as a product in 13% yields, whose genesis could be understood on the basis of elimination followed by oxidation of the resulting cinnamic acid. This diversion could partly account for the lower yields⁸. At pH 6, both phenylalanine (**1**) and tyrosine (**2**) are transformed by path b (Scheme 3) to, as primary oxidation products, phenylacetic acid (**3**) and *p*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid, which unlike **3** undergoes further oxidation to malonic acid (**5**) (*vide infra*).

It is pertinent to note here that when the availability of nitrogen lone-pair is blocked and the duration of the oxidation prolonged, the phenyl ring is exclusively transformed to a carboxyl unit. Thus, *N*-acetylphenylalanine methyl ester (**8**), under the usual conditions at pH 6, but for prolonged periods (60 h), gave exclusively *N*-acetylaspartic acid- α -methyl ester (**9**) in 70% yields (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

In the absence of acetonitrile, no oxidation could be observed, thus highlighting the key role played by this solvent in maintaining a proper Ru^{VIII} concentration in the organic phase. Parenthetically, it is likely that the dilution of carbon tetrachloride with acetonitrile would, as a result of decreased density of the organic phase, increase the interfacial surface area, thus further promoting the oxidation⁹.

A serendipitous finding that has emerged from the present study is that the oxidation of the benzene ring is highly sensitive to perturbations arising from substitution. Whilst this may be evident in the ready oxidation of *p*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid to malonic acid (**5**) (Scheme 1), contrasted to the inertness of the parent phenylacetic acid (**3**) (Scheme 2), our studies have shown that in many cases this factor can be subtle. For example, under conditions of the **8** \rightarrow **9** change (Scheme 4) and that reported for the transformation of benzyl ethers to benzoates¹⁰, *N*-benzyloxycarbonylglycine methyl ester (**Z-Gly-OMe**) is totally recovered unchanged (this was fortunate, since it permitted oxidations of many *Z*-protected- α -amino acid side-chains). Thus the remote CO unit of benzyloxycarbonyl, protected the aryl residue from Ru^{VIII} oxidation. As expected, *N*-benzyloxycarbonylglycine methyl ester (**Bz-Gly-OMe**) was also not affected. This property has enabled,

inter alia, the transformation of *N*-benzyloxycarbonylphenylalanine methyl ester (**Z-Phe-OMe**) (**10**) to *N*-benzyloxycarbonylaspartic acid- α -methyl ester (**Z-Asp**(β -OH)-**OMe**) (**11**) in 85% yields (Scheme 5). We believe that the preferential oxidation of aryl units in multiple aryl containing substrates is easily feasible.

Scheme 5

A noteworthy feature is that the preference for ring oxidation in the case of PhCH₂CH- is changed to that for benzylic CH₂ with heteroatom perturbation, as exemplified with the PhCH₂O- unit¹⁰. Additionally, conjugation of the heteroatom with carbonyl makes the substrate inert (PhCH₂OCONH-, PhCH₂OCO-).

The preparation of chiral glycine has been reported from chiral benzylamine, either by direct oxidation with Ru^{VIII}, generated with hypochlorite (39%) or via sequence, acetylation, ozonolysis and enzymatic hydrolysis (52% overall)⁶. Whilst the latter pathway was quite in agreement with our findings, the former appeared quite unusual, particularly since the household bleach used in the experiment usually has a pH 11¹¹. In our hands, attempted oxidation of benzylamine under these conditions gave no glycine but an intractable dark mixture. Our findings agree with the reported⁷ observations that the reaction of Ru^{VIII} - generated and transferred to carbon tetrachloride - with benzylamine at pH 4.5 gave a low yield of glycine, with dramatic improvement (60%) at pH 3. Thus it appears that the vital information pertaining to the need to keep the pH low to secure chiral glycine from benzylamine precursor seems to have been left out in this report⁶. Finally, oxidation of benzylamine with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6, under our conditions, gave a complex mixture and the only crystalline product that was obtained in 3% yield was benzylbenzamide (**12**), thus demonstrating that to this extent at least, the phenyl ring was untouched (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

The perturbation of the benzene ring environments on the course of its oxidation has been the focus thus far. This has been complemented with the demonstration of selectivity, principally arising from differences in amino group basicity, with lysine (13) as the substrate. The reasonable difference that exists between the pK_a of the α -amino (pK_a 8.95) and the ω -amino (pK_a 10.53) groups, suggested possibilities for the preferential oxidation of the less basic α -amino group of lysine. This was experimentally realized. Thus, lysine (13) either at pH 3 or even at pH 6, gave, as the sole isolable product, glutaric acid monoamide (14), in respectively, 34 and 33% yields. At the higher pH of 9, no pure products could be isolated. The 13 \rightarrow 14 change can be readily understood on the basis of the expected exclusive N^α -amino group oxidation to 5-aminopentanoic acid, cyclization to piperidone, further oxidation to glutarimide¹² and hydrolysis (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Experimental support for the above pathway has been obtained from studies with N^ω -benzyloxycarbonyl lysine (N^ω -lys) (15) and N^α -benzyloxycarbonyl lysine (N^α -Z-lys) (16). In the case of 15, whilst the first stage of oxidation leading to the piperidone was expected, its further oxidation to glutarimide was anticipated to be difficult because of the de-activating influence of the benzyloxycarbonyl moiety. In the event, the reaction of 15 with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6 afforded N -benzyloxycarbonylpiperidone (17; 21%) and N -benzyloxycarbonyl-5-aminopentanoic acid (18; 30%), thus further reinforcing many of the conclusions drawn from the present study (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

As anticipated, N^α -benzyloxycarbonyllysine (16) was found unaffected on treatment with Ru^{VIII} species at pH 3 as well as at pH 6. Finally, N^α -benzyloxycarbonylarginine ethyl ester (N^α -Z-Arg-OEt) was recovered on attempted oxidation with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6 as well as at pH 3.

The significance of these results lies in the fact that at pH 3 certainly, and even at pH 6, lysine and arginine side-chains can be made insensitive to ruthenium oxidations. The site-specific transformation of (trp)melittin to (asp)melittin³, in presence of unprotected lysine and arginine is an example of this understanding¹³.

The genesis of our interest in Ru^{VIII} species is the realization that 11 of the 20 coded amino acid side-chains are susceptible to this reagent and consequently the delineation of preferences would enable site-specific peptide alteration. The present work is one of the many probes that were explored to realize this objective.

Experimental

All amino acids used are of L-configuration. Ir spectra were recorded on PE 580/377/1600 (FT) instruments, nmr spectra on WP80/R 600 (FT) spectrometers and mass spectra on a Jeol instrument. Elemental analyses were performed on automatic analyzers. Silica gel was used for tlc and column chromatography (100–200 mesh). Reactions were monitored wherever possible by tlc. The organic extracts were invariably dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and solvents evaporated *in vacuo*.

Reaction of tyrosine (2) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 3. Isolation of aspartic acid (4): A solution of tyrosine (2; 0.72 g, 4 mmol) in MeCN (16 ml) was admixed with CCl_4 : pH 3 phosphate buffer (1 : 2; 48 ml), $NaIO_4$ (15.4 g, 72 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.03 g, 2.2 mol%), left stirred for 3 h, pH adjusted to ≈ 6 by addition of aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, the residue washed with CCl_4 (3×10 ml), the filtrate saturated with NaCl, the layers separated and the aqueous layer extracted with EtOAc (3×25 ml). The combined organic extracts were dried and evaporated to afford negligible amounts of neutral residue.

The aqueous layer was continuously extracted with ether for 4 days. Aspartic acid was crystallized in the ether extract over the period of extraction. Evaporation of the ether afforded aspartic acid (4; 0.27 g, 50%) m.p. $>300^\circ$, identical in all respects with an authentic sample.

Reaction of tyrosine (2) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Isolation of malonic acid (5): A mixture of tyrosine (2; 0.72 g, 4 mmol) in MeCN : CCl_4 : H_2O (1 : 1 : 2; 64 ml), $NaIO_4$ (15.4 g, 72 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.030 g, 2.2 mol%) was left stirred for 3 h and processed as described previously, without pH adjustment. The combined organic extracts yielded malonic acid (5; 0.084 g, 20%), m.p. $135\text{--}37^\circ$ (water), identical in all respects to an authentic sample.

The aqueous layer was continuously ether extracted for 4 days. The ether extract on evaporation did not yield aspartic acid.

Reaction of tyrosine (2) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 9. Isolation

of malonic acid (5) in enhanced yields : A mixture of tyrosine (2; 0.72 g, 4 mmol) in MeCN : CCl₄ : satd. sodium bicarbonate (pH ≈ 9) (1 : 1 : 2; 64 ml), NaIO₄ (15.4 g, 72 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.030 g, 2.2 mol%) was left stirred for 3 h. Work-up as described previously, after adjustment of pH to ≈ 6 with 2N H₂SO₄, gave malonic acid (0.200 g, 48%).

The aqueous layer was continuously ether extracted for 4 days. The ether extract on evaporation did not yield aspartic acid.

Reaction of phenylalanine (1) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 3. Isolation of phenylacetic acid (3) : A solution of phenylalanine (1; 0.661 g, 4 mmol) in MeCN (16 ml) was admixed with CCl₄ : pH 3 phosphate buffer (1 : 2, 48 ml), NaIO₄ (15.48 g, 72 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.030 g, 2.2 mol%), left stirred for 3 h, adjusted to pH 6 with aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, the residue washed with CCl₄ (3 × 10 ml), the filtrate saturated with NaCl, layers separated, the aqueous layer extracted with EtOAc (3 × 25 ml) and the combined organic layers dried and evaporated. The residue was digested with satd. aqueous bicarbonate (30 ml) for 3 h, extracted with ether (2 × 10 ml), the aqueous layer adjusted to pH 3 with 2N H₂SO₄, saturated with NaCl, extracted with EtOAc (3 × 25 ml), dried and evaporated to give phenylacetic acid (3; 0.414 g, 76%), m.p. 76–77°, whose properties were identical to that of an authentic sample.

Continuous ether extraction of the primary aqueous layer, as described previously, did not yield any aspartic acid.

Reaction of phenylalanine (1) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Isolation of phenylacetic acid (3) : The oxidation as described above was carried out with phenylalanine (1; 0.661 g) in MeCN : CCl₄ : H₂O (1 : 1 : 2; 64 ml), but with no pH adjustment after the reaction. The residue from the combined organic layers was digested with satd. aqueous bicarbonate and further processed as above. Tlc of the acid residue showed the presence of benzoic acid. The latter (0.06 g, 13%; m.p. 120–121°) was removed by trituration with small amounts of hot dry benzene. The benzene extract on evaporation gave phenylacetic acid (3; 0.234 g, 43%), m.p. 76–77°.

Continuous ether extraction of the primary aqueous layer did not afford any aspartic acid.

Reaction of N-acetylphenylalanine methyl ester [Ac-Phe-OMe] (8) with Ru^{VIII}. Isolation of N-acetylaspartic acid- α -methyl ester [Ac-Asp(β -OH)-OMe] (9) : A solution of Ac-Phe-OMe (8; 0.8 g, 3.62 mmol) in MeCN (14.5 ml) admixed with CCl₄ : H₂O (1 : 2; 43.5 ml), NaIO₄ (13.94 g, 65.16 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.027 g, 2.2 mol%) was left shaken for 60 h, filtered, the residue washed with CCl₄ (3 × 10 ml), layers separated, the aqueous layer extracted with EtOAc (3 × 25 ml), the combined organic extracts dried,

evaporated, the residue digested with saturated aqueous bicarbonate (30 ml, 3 h), extracted with ether (2 × 10 ml), adjusted to pH 3 with 2N H₂SO₄, extracted with EtOAc (3 × 25 ml), dried and evaporated to afford Ac-Asp(β -OH)-OMe (9; 0.471 g, 70%), which was identified via esterification with diazomethane and comparison with authentic sample, m.p. 56–57° (benzene-hexane); nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.05 (3H, s), 2.95 (2H, m), 3.7 (3H, s), 3.75 (3H, s), 4.9 (1H, m), 6.45–6.95 (1H, br).

Reaction of N-benzyloxycarbonylglycine methyl ester [Z-Gly-OMe] with Ru^{VIII}. Demonstration of protecting group (Z) unreactivity : A solution of Z-Gly-OMe (0.650 g, 2.9 mmol) in MeCN (12 ml) was admixed with CCl₄ : H₂O (1 : 2, 36 ml), NaIO₄ (11.55 g, 54 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.023 g, 2.2 mol%) and left shaken for 60 h at room temperature, filtered, the residue washed with CCl₄ (3 × 10 ml), layers separated, the aqueous layer extracted with EtOAc (3 × 20 ml), the combined organic extracts dried and evaporated to give pure starting material (0.600 g, 92%).

Reaction of N-benzyloxycarbonylphenylalanine methyl ester [Z-Phe-OMe] (10) with Ru^{VIII}. Isolation of N-benzyloxycarbonylaspartic acid- α -methyl ester [Z-Asp(β -OH)-OMe] (11) : A solution of Z-Phe-OMe (1.2 g, 3.83 mmol) in MeCN (15.3 ml) was admixed with CCl₄ : H₂O (1 : 2, 46 ml), NaIO₄ (14.75 g, 69 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.029 g, 2.2 mol%), sealed, left shaken for 60 h and processed as described in Experiment for isolation of 9, to yield Z-Asp(β -OH)-OMe (11; 0.911 g, 85%) as a gum; nmr δ (CDCl₃) 3.0 (2H, m), 3.7 (3H, s), 5.1 (2H, s), 4.6 (1H, m), 5.8 (1H, m), 7.2 (5H, s).

Compound 11 was further characterized as its dimethyl ester, Z-Asp(β -OMe)-OMe; ν_{\max} (neat) 3330, 1710, 1495, 1430 cm⁻¹; nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.9 (2H, m), 3.6 (3H, s), 3.7 (3H, s), 4.55 (1H, m), 5.05 (2H, s), 5.65 (1H, m), 7.25 (5H, s).

Reaction of lysine (13) at pH 3 with Ru^{VIII}. Isolation of glutaric acid monoamide (14) : A mixture of lysine monohydrochloride (0.73 g, 4 mmol), MeCN : CCl₄ : pH 3 phosphate buffer (1 : 1 : 2; 64 ml), NaIO₄ (15.4 g, 72 mmol) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.030 g, 2.2 mol%) was left stirred for 3 h, pH adjusted to 6 by addition of aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, the residue washed with CCl₄ (3 × 10 ml), the filtrate saturated with NaCl, layers separated, the aqueous layer extracted with EtOAc (3 × 25 ml), dried and evaporated to give glutaric acid mono amide (14; 0.18 g, 34%), m.p. 102° (lit.¹⁴ 96–98°) (Found : C, 45.66; H, 7.2; N, 10.34. C₅H₉O₃N calcd. for : C, 45.80; H, 6.87; N, 10.69%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3310, 1685, 1620, 1520 cm⁻¹; nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.8 (2H, m), 2.3 (2H, m), 3.25 (2H, m), 7.1 (2H, br).

Compound 14 was further characterized using ice-cooled diazo methane to the methyl ester, oil : nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.9

(2H, m), 2.35 (2H, t), 3.3 (2H, m), 3.65 (3H, s), 8.1 (2H, br), m/z 145 (M^+).

Reaction of lysine (13) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Isolation of glutaric acid monoamide (14): A solution of lysine monohydrochloride (0.73 g, 4 mmol) in water (5 ml) was adjusted to pH 6 by addition of aqueous bicarbonate, admixed with MeCN : CCl_4 : H_2O (16 : 16 : 27 ml), $NaIO_4$ (15.4 g, 72 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.030 g, 2.2 mol%) and left stirred for 3 h. Work up, without adjustment of pH, as described in the previous experiment afforded glutaric acid monoamide (14; 0.173 g, 33%).

Reaction of N^ω -benzyloxycarbonyllysine [N^ω -Z-Lys] (15) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Isolation of N -benzyloxycarbonyl-2-piperidone (17) and N -benzyloxycarbonyl-5-aminopentanoic acid (18): A mixture of N^ω -Z-lys (15; 0.280 g, 1 mmol), MeCN : CCl_4 : H_2O (1 : 1 : 2; 16 ml) and $NaIO_4$ (3.924 g, 18 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.0075 g, 2.2 mol%) was sealed, left shaken for 3 h, filtered, the residue washed with hot EtOAc (3 \times 5 ml), layers separated, dried, evaporated, the residue digested with saturated aqueous bicarbonate (10 ml, 3 h), extracted with EtOAc (3 \times 10 ml) dried and evaporated to afford N -benzyloxycarbonyl-2-piperidone (17; 0.05 g, 21%) as a gum; ν_{max} (neat) 1705, 1530 cm^{-1} ; nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.66 (4H, m), 2.38 (2H, m), 3.25 (2H, m), 5.1 (2H, s), 7.38 (5H, s).

The bicarbonate extract was adjusted to pH 3 with 2N H_2SO_4 , extracted with EtOAc (3 \times 10 ml), dried and evaporated to give N -benzyloxycarbonyl-5-aminopentanoic acid (18; 0.075 g, 30%) as a solid; ν_{max} (KBr) 3318, 1692, 1532 cm^{-1} ; nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.69 (4H, m), 2.31 (2H, m), 3.18 (2H, m), 5.1 (2H, s), 7.3 (5H, s), 9.1 (1H, br).

Reaction of N^α -benzyloxycarbonyllysine (N^α -Z-Lys-OH) (16) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 3. Demonstration of side-chain unreactivity: A mixture of N^α -Z-Lys-OH (16; 0.100 g, 0.35 mmol), MeCN : CCl_4 : pH 3 phosphate buffer (1 : 1 : 2; 4.5 ml), $NaIO_4$ (1.374 g, 6.275 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.003 g, 2.2 mol%) was stirred at room temperature for 18 h, pH adjusted to \approx 6 by addition of aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, the residue washed with CCl_4 (3 \times 10 ml), the combined filtrates evaporated to dryness, the residue triturated with hot MeOH (6 \times 10 ml) and the methanolic extracts on evaporation yielded unchanged (16, 0.072 g). No other product could be isolated.

Reaction of N^α -benzyloxycarbonyllysine (N^α -Z-Lys-OH) (16) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Demonstration of side-chain unreactivity: Treatment of N^α -Z-Lys-OH (16; 0.100 g, 0.35 mmol) in MeCN : CCl_4 : water (1 : 1 : 2; 4.5 ml) with $NaIO_4$ (1.374 g, 6.275 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.003 g, 2.2 mol%) and work-up as described above without pH adjustment, afforded unchanged 16 (0.080 g).

Reaction of N^α -benzoylarginine ethyl ester hydrochloride

[Bz-Arg-OEt.HCl] (19) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 3. Demonstration of side-chain unreactivity: A mixture of Bz-Arg-OEt.HCl (19; 0.172 g, 0.5 mmol), MeCN : CCl_4 : pH 3 phosphate buffer (1 : 1 : 2; 8 ml), $NaIO_4$ (1.925 g, 9 mmol) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.004 g, 2.2 mol%) was left stirred at room temperature for 60 h, pH adjusted to 6 by addition of aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, the residue washed with CCl_4 (3 \times 10 ml), the combined filtrates evaporated to dryness and triturated with MeOH (5 \times 5 ml). The methanolic extract on evaporation gave crude Bz-Arg-OEt (0.137 g) which was taken up in water (5 ml) and passed through a column of IRA 400 Cl^- (regenerated with 0.1N HCl). Evaporation afforded 0.093 g of pure starting material. No other products could be isolated.

Reaction of N^α -benzoylarginine ethyl ester hydrochloride [Bz-Arg-OEt.HCl] (19) with Ru^{VIII} at pH 6. Demonstration of side-chain unreactivity: Bz-Arg-OEt.HCl (19; 0.172 g, 0.5 mmol) was dissolved in water (3 ml), pH adjusted to 6 with aqueous bicarbonate, admixed with MeCN : CCl_4 (1 : 1, 3 ml), $NaIO_4$ (1.925 g, 9 mmol), $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.004 g, 2.2 mol%) and left stirred for 100 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture, when processed, without pH adjustment; precisely as described in the previous experiment, afforded pure unchanged starting material (0.071 g). No other product could be isolated.

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References

1. The volt equivalent parameter provides a convenient measure of the oxidizing capability. The values are derived from standard reduction potentials in acidic aqueous solution. It would be interesting to compare the value for Ru^{VIII} (8.698) with ozone (9.068), Os^{VIII} (6.8), Fe^{III} (6.49) (N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNshaw, "Chemistry of Elements", Pergamon, Oxford, 1986, p. 1251).
2. J. L. COURTNEY, 'Ruthenium Tetroxide Oxidations' in "Organic Synthesis by Oxidation with Metal Compounds", eds. W. J. MUIJ and C. R. H. I. DE JONGE, Plenum, New York, 1986, p. 445.
3. S. RANGANATHAN, D. RANGANATHAN, S. BAMEZAI, W. P. SINGH, D. BHATTACHARYYA, G. P. SINGH, R. RATHI, N. JAYARAMAN and B. K. PATEL, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1990, **62**, 1437.
4. P. H. J. CARLSON, T. KATASUKI, V. S. MARTIN and B. K. SHARPLESS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **46**, 3936.
5. D. C. AYRES, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1975, 440.
6. M. KAJIWARA, S. -F. LEE, I. A. SCOTT, M. AKHTAR, C. R. JONES and P. M. JORDAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 967.
7. D. C. AYRES, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1978, 585.
8. It is possible that small yields (\approx 5%) of malonic acid could have escaped detection.

9. Interface area could be increased by lowering the density of the organic phase (CCl_4). It is planned to examine this aspect on the course of the oxidation.
10. P. F. SCHUDA, M. B. CICHOWICZ and M. R. HEINMAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 3829.
11. N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNSHAW, "Chemistry of Elements", Pergamon, Oxford, 1986, p. 1006.
12. The transformation of *N*-substituted piperidines to glutarimides has been reported (F. MORLACCHI, V. LOSACCO and V. TORTORELLA, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, **16**, 297).
13. It is pertinent to note that, in the case of lysine, when the N^α and N^ω as well as the carboxyl groupings are protected, the methylene adjacent to the N^ω is preferentially oxidized, further illustrating the controls that can be brought about in Ru^{VIII} oxidations. Thus, N^α , N^ω bis *t*-butoxycarbonyllysine benzyl ester in $\text{EtOAc} : \text{MeCN} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ medium affords N^α , N^ω bis *t*-butoxycarbonylhomoglutamine benzyl ester (S. YOSHIFUJI, K. TANAKA and Y. NITTA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1985, **33**, 1749; N. SAKURA, K. HIROSE and T. HASHIMOTO, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1985, **33**, 1752).
14. G. H. JEFFERY and A. I. VOGEL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1103.